

Global Bioinformatics Education Summit Day 5

**Bioinformatics training on different
scales - sharing knowledge and
leveraging global connections**

Agenda

Day 5			
TIME (CST) Link to timezone	SESSION TOPIC + Session Content Hyperlink	PRESENTER	LOCATION
8:30 - 9:00 a.m.	Arrival		
9:00 - 09:30	Welcome, setting the scene Invited case studies	Katharina F Heil	CIEE 401 Alpha Zoom
09:30 - 10:30	Present your Training Community <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Complete your own Community card - Breakouts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the common challenges - which themes emerge (regional/scale/topic) Outcome: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - List of challenges - scale/regional/topic specific? - Aim for very specific list with a clear focus on regional capacity building <i>PS: Use the working document for notes</i>	Lisanna / Geert. Yalbi Balderas (local support)	CIEE 401 Alpha Zoom
10:30 - 10:50	Break		
10:50 - 12:00	Finding solutions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Breakouts <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Solutions for the presented challenges <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Do you have experience in cross-regional collaboration? - What worked and what didn't? <i>PS: Use the working document for notes</i>	Rolanda Julius	CIE401 Alpha Zoom
12:00 - 12:30	Wrap-up and next steps	Lisanna, Katharina F Heil, Rolanda Julius	CIE401 Alpha Zoom
13:30 - 13:00	Final conference wrap-up		CIE401 Alpha Zoom
13:00 - 13:10	Closing	Jorge Teodoro Chedraui Urrea	CIE401 Alpha Zoom

Community cards

The community cards help to understand training communities or projects, and how they work.

The cards have been used to:

- Cluster similar communities or training efforts.
- Identify common challenges and shared needs.
- Support regional and global coordination of training efforts.
- Raise awareness about each other's initiatives and establish contacts!

Cards by Scale

- Global

- [AgBioData](#)
- [DS-I Africa](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)
- [SoiBio](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Within one/multiple institutions

- [Bio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [ELIXIR](#)
- [NGS Academy for the Africa PGI](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [Unidad de Ciencia de Datos en Salud](#)

- Within one Country

- [Australian BioCommons](#)
- [Canadian Bioinformatics Hub](#)
- [de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE](#)
- [Red Mexicana de Bioinformatica](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [Unidad de Ciencia de Datos en Salud](#)

Cards by Region

- Africa

- [AgBioData](#)
- [DS-I Africa](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [NGS Academy for the Africa PGI](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- North America

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Canadian Bioinformatics Hub](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Latin America

- [AgBioData](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)
- [Red Mexicana de Bioinformatica](#)
- [SoiBio](#)
- [UCDS](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Europe

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Bio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ELIXIR](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Asia

- [AgBioData](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Australia

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Australian BioCommons](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

Cards by Keywords

- Bioinformatics

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Australian BioCommons](#)
- [Canadian Bioinformatics Hub](#)
- [de.NBI](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [NGS Academy for the Africa PGI](#)
- [Red Mexicana de Bioinformatica](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [SoiBio](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Data Science

- [AgBioData](#)
- [DS-I Africa](#)
- [UCDS](#)

- Open Science

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Bio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)

- Training

- [AgBioDataBio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [Canadian Bioinformatics Hub](#)
- [de.NBI](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [Ensembl](#)
- [ISCB COSI](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)
- [Red Mexicana de Bioinformatica](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Community

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Australian BioCommons](#)
- [Bio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [EMBL-EBI](#)
- [ISCB](#)
- [MetaDocencia](#)
- [Red Mexicana de Bioinformatica](#)
- [SIB](#)
- [Wellcome Connecting Science](#)

- Infrastructure

- [AgBioData](#)
- [Australian BioCommons](#)
- [Bio-IT/Data Science](#)
- [ELIXIR](#)

Community cards

- Shared in alphabetical order of the communities they represent

What is your community?

AgBioData

Ensuring that high-quality agricultural data complies with FAIR principles

#agbiodata #FAIRdata #agriculturaldatabases
#bioinformaticseducation

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

Bring together cross-functional teams to review existing data management practices, identify challenges and make recommendations to promote the adoption of FAIR data standards, formats and best practices.

Deliver hands-on training courses and educational materials & disseminate scientific content to the Ag community.

Co-write and share white papers, newsletters

Review existing and co-develop new software tools

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Marcela Karey Tello-Ruiz. AgBioData.org

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text.

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? The consortium involves >40 Ag DBs and associated resources worldwide (data repository leaders, developers, curators, users, librarians, funders, publishers).

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Creating learning modules is not a priority for bioinformaticians not actively teaching	Created monetary awards for independent contributors
Writing a white paper is a challenging task delegated to one individual with a full workload	Incentive awards and recognition for manuscript writing and project leadership
Promoting educational resources by attending meetings might be challenging for non-educators	Appoint ambassadors to promote educational resources at key conferences with participating educators

What is your community?

Australian
BioCommons

Who we are: Australian BioCommons

Our audience: Australian life science community

Our goal: build bioinformatics skills and support the life science community to learn how to use new and existing platforms, tools, services and techniques.

Keywords: national, community scale, research infrastructure, bioinformatics

How does it work?

BioCommons supports specialists from across Australia to deliver training resources and events at a national scale.

We do this by convening the National Bioinformatics Training cooperative, a collective of local training providers that collaborates to bring excellent local training to a national audience.

All training is delivered online to a geographically dispersed audience. Example outputs: workshops, webinars, collections of resources, training needs survey

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Melissa Burke, Training Manager, Australian BioCommons

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Yes. Primarily nationally. Occasionally internationally e.g. with ELIXIR

Lessons learned

Outcomes/Solution / strategies

Working collaboratively national and local benefits

- Boosts awareness of local training and support
- More topics available in all locations
- Trainers learn new skills from each other
- Stronger training network that has sparked independent collaborations

Collaboration needs dedicated coordination and continual relationship building

Have a dedicated community manager who's role it is to nurture the collaboration and coordinate activities

Resourcing and turnover of staff is a challenge

As above. A work in progress.

Time zones!

An example of how we've collaborated across time zones

What is your community?

Vision: To accelerate the growth of a dynamic health and life sciences sector in Canada by building Bioinformatics, Computational Biology and Data Science capacity

#training #community #capacity #careerdevelopment

How does it work?

We aim to:

- Build and strengthen Bioinformatics, Computational Biology, and Data Science (BCBDS) capacity in Canada through the Canadian Bioinformatics Workshops.
- Support trainees' and Early Career Researchers' professional development and engagement in BCBDS sectors in Canada with mentorship opportunities and awards.
- Foster diverse and inclusive BCBDS communities throughout Canada.

Find out more at bioinformatics.ca/about

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card authors: Michelle D. Brazas, Larisa M. Soto, Nia Hughes, Alexandra Smith

Which is your region? And scale?

Pan-Canadian

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Yes, we collaborate with other national and regional institutions & organizations, and occasionally with international groups (e.g. CSHL)

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Canada is really big!	Distributed workshops; coordinators embedded in each region; resourcing local communities
Fragmented scientific community	Developing infrastructure to connect communities; national conference
Training programs are not fully accessible or scalable	Training trainers; overarching IDEA Framework; mapping competencies

What is your community?

Data Science / Bio-IT community Fostering computational biology and data science activities at EMBL

#consulting #training #infrastructure #community
#openScience #careerDevelopment

How does it work?

Meet regularly to discuss needs and collaborative actions

Experts' consulting and live troubleshooting

Hands-on training courses

Software infrastructure for (scientific) collaboration

Onboarding, information sharing, volunteer contributions

Link to EMBL stakeholders (other training providers, policy-making entities, core facilities, IT ...)

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Lisanna Paladin

Which is your region? And scale?

Across EMBL's six sites in Europe, >2000 employees

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We collaborate across countries in Europe, career paths and sometimes with external entities.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Recognition of voluntary contributions	Champions page, certificates and support letter under request, <i>what else?</i>
Training across sites	Improved hybrid format
Limited awareness of the services offered	Onboarding, dedicated events, comms standardisation
Specificity of expertise / jobs in the team	Stimulating wider discussion at international level, interaction with policies

What is your community?

de.NBI ELIXIR-DE Training Grouping trainers and training organisers in bioinformatics in Germany

#training #bioinformatics #computationalBiology

How does it work?

Meet bi-monthly to exchange on common practices, topics and shared events

Linked to bigger initiatives (de.NBI in Germany, ELIXIR in Europe)

Specific about training in bioinformatics, computational biology, data science

Some common components of infrastructure (e.g. de.NBI Cloud), but wide heterogeneity of institutional practices, databases, etc.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Lisanna Paladin

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We collaborate across countries in Europe, career paths and sometimes with external entities.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies (<u>suggested</u>)
Enhance Trainers recognition	Certification system Website and media visibility
Resources accessibility	Centralised and FAIR materials Technical support for workshops Dedicated budget
Foster collaboration	Peer consulting, exchange program
No training-dedicated compensation	New funding models, embedding in contracts

What is your community?

DS-I Africa
Data Science for Health Discovery
and Innovation in Africa

The Data Science for Health Discovery and Innovation in Africa (DS-I Africa) Initiative aims to leverage data science technologies to transform biomedical and public health research and develop solutions that would lead to improved health for individuals and populations..

#biomedical #machine learning #Africa #health innovation

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

Co create and develop training opportunities through the Training and Education WG

Source and enable access to external training opportunities

Develop in-house biomedical data science training

Support health data science degree programmes across Africa

Engage in biomedical data science research, and cross-country data sharing policy development

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Rolanda Julius; dsi-africa.org;

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text.

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent: 23 African

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Please comment, and if so fill the next slide too. Otherwise, remove it.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community distributed in a large area	Online events increase accessibility, annual in-person meeting
Diverse interests, data science multidisciplinary field	Provide diverse training topics, tier offerings of introductory, advanced etc
Trainers not professionally recognised	Developed trainers registry hosted on website to showcase skills and qualifications of trainers in consortium

What is your community?

Teaching scientists around the world how to use Ensembl in their work.

#genomics #genes #annotation #training #ensembl

How does it work?

Deliver hands-on in-person and remote training courses.

Teach Ensembl as part of university courses and academic programmes.

Organise and run *Train the Trainer* workshops to empower local trainers to deliver their own Ensembl workshops.

Provide open-access training materials, tutorials, and helpdesk support to users worldwide.

Offer tailored training and support for institutions and researchers, adapting content to specific needs and research interests.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lessons learned from your activity?

Card authors: Louise Paola Mirabueno, Aleena Mushtaq Stolworthy

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales?

EMBL-EBI training, H3Africa, DIPLOMICS, local ISCB Regional Student Groups, DKFZ

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Ensuring effective learning and skill retention	Emphasise practical, hands-on training and provide accessible materials for ongoing learning
Limited local expertise in some regions	Empower trainers through <i>Train the Trainer</i> programmes and capacity building in the local language
Keeping resources relevant and user-centered	Engage users continuously for feedback and integrate their insights into resource development

What is your community?

EMBL-EBI

The Training Team coordinates EMBL-EBI's training and scientific outreach activities, delivering an extensive training programme in bioinformatics and data science.

#bioinformatics-training #capacity-strengthening #on-demand-training #partnerships #EMBLEBI

How does it work?

We run courses - in person at EMBL-EBI and virtually, knowledge exchange and training activities with our partners within and outside EMBL-EBI, and offer open-access on-demand elearning.

Live training: Deliver in-person and virtual training courses

On-demand training: an extensive catalog of webinars, online tutorials, collections (learning pathways) and materials from our live courses

Support trainers: provide opportunities for skills development including train the trainer courses

Partnerships: collaborate through grant funded activities and community endeavours.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Patricia Carvajal-López/Aziz Mithani/Kim Gurwitz

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We collaborate with partners across the world to deliver training, build competence and capacity, and empower scientists to gain new scientific insights and to build new services (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/training/our-partnerships>).

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community distributed in a large area	Online events and ondemand content increase accessibility
Keeping trainees and trainers up to date in fast-pace field	Regularly refresh our training content, engage in cutting-edge grant-funded projects and communities

www.ebi.ac.uk/training

What is your community?

The ELIXIR Training Platform spans all 23 ELIXIR member states.

- Training Coordinators
- Training Platform members

#ELIXIR #ResearchInfrastructure #distributed

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate.

- Work Programme part of ELIXIR's technical scientific programme
 - Representatives from all member states ("Training Coordinators")
 - Strengthen national training programmes
 - Grow bioinformatics training capacity and competence across Europe
 - Empower researchers to use ELIXIR's services and tools
 - Work on the training life cycle:
- <https://elixir-europe-training.github.io/ELIXIR-Training-SPLASH/>

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Katharina F Heil

Which is your region? And scale?

All ELIXIR member states (23), each has a Training Coordinator, representing national training activities.

Circle the one(s):

- Institution
- Group of institutes
- Area
- Country
- Continent
- Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales?

- Individual ELIXIR countries/members states
- Other global initiatives (GOBLET-ELIXIR Training Strategy)

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community distributed in a large area	Regular (online and F2F) community building events
Resources	Join efforts
Distributed (can also be an advantage)	Specific liaisons - direct connection to (user) communities

📷 What is your community?

#LatinAmerica #community
#OpenScience #training

We build scientific and technical capacities with a local and responsible perspective. We co-create networks, learning spaces, and resources for Spanish-speaking researchers and communities.

🔧 How does it work?

Active, online short format training and 6-week long cohorts, including

- good practices for online teaching
- Open Science
- grant writing

Steward a supportive network that fosters collaborations and the dissemination of knowledge

Create open, high-quality scientific material, or adapt to Spanish attending to local needs

Promote access to better infrastructure and funding

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Nicolás Palopoli and www.metadocencia.org

🎯 Which is your region? And scale?

From **Latin America** to the whole world – we trained people from **33 countries**, and reach over **2500 persons globally**

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We've had over 40 partners and sponsors – join our *Hive of Fellow Communities!*

<http://bit.ly/md-hive>

📄 Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Less visibility for researchers in the Global South	Build connections: >1000 Slack members, >6000 social media followers
Limited access to resources and training	Open, free training and resources + funding support
Language barriers	Contextualization to Spanish
Community development and sustainability	Support governance development + collaborate in grant applications

What is your community?

The ISCB Education Community of Special Interest (COSI) is a global community meant to bring together those working with ISCB and others in bioinformatics education worldwide.

Bioinformatics computational biology education

How does it work?

Examples of ISCB Education COSI activities:

Organize the educational program at ISMB and promote educational content at other ISCB-affiliated meetings

Create new initiatives such as the ISCB competencies effort and its degree program endorsement process

Participate in other activities of the community, such as the Bioinformatics Education Summit

Act as a bridge between ISCB's Education Committee and other organizations, such as GOBLET

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Russell Schwartz

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text.

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We work at scales from the regional to the global.

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community distributed in a large area	Online/hybrid events and presence at regional meetings
Many groups have arisen to take on similar challenges	Outreach, promoting communication between education groups
Trainers often lack funding for meetings/professional development	Allow different modes of participation and raise support for attendees

What is your community?

Who we are: National Microbiology Laboratory
Our audience: Canadian Public Health employees
Our goal: To build and support capacity development in genomics and bioinformatics across the Canadian laboratory health network

#bioinformatics #public health #capacity development
 #career development

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

Deliver synchronous and asynchronous hands-on training courses in basic coding and bioinformatics.

Co-develop documentation for end users.

Recruit subject matter experts from within the network.

Foster diverse and inclusive knowledge sharing communities throughout Canada.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Sonal Shewaramani

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text.

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Please comment, and if so fill the next slide too. Otherwise, remove it.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community is distributed over a large area - thus is very fragmented and lots of bureaucratic hurdles are involved.	Online events increase accessibility and networking opportunities; working on building community connections
Limited resources - personnel, money, infrastructure etc.	Increasing collaboration and using methods to incentivize people
Training provided needs to be accessible and bilingual	Working on translating materials, and incorporating accessibility

What is your community?

NGS Academy for the Africa PGI

Developing Bioinformatics Capacity for Genomic Epidemiology and Pathogen Surveillance in Africa

#public health bioinformatics #pathogen surveillance

How does it work?

- Deliver in-person training and present online training in response to, and in preparation for, disease outbreaks.
- Develop a standardized curriculum for pathogen genomics, in partnership with experts across Africa and globally.
- Build communities around pathogens of interest and bioinformatics skills development.
- Facilitate the development of bioinformatics workflows for relevant pathogens.
- Provide travel fellowships to enable participants to present their work at bioinformatics conferences.

Card author: Kirsty Lee Garson

Which is your region? And scale?

- Institution
- Group of institutes
- Area
- Country
- **Continent**
- Global
- Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales?

Public Health Alliance for Genomic Epidemiology (PHA4GE) - global

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solutions/strategies
Sustainability and funding	Leverage regional networks, identify training partners
Need for sustained engagement to develop capacity effectively	Communities of practice, locally based trainers
Developing collaborations, mentorship relationships outside of training events, ongoing support	Trainer database, helpdesk ticketing system

What is your community?

The Peruvian Society for Bioinformatics and Computational Biology

We actively promote knowledge sharing, diversity, equity and inclusion in bioinformatics through multiple training and networking events in Peru. We support the Regional Student Group - Peru.

#spbcb #rsg_peru #bioinformatics #peru
#computational_biology

How does it work?

We organize free bioinformatic training events in Spanish, both remote or hybrid

We offer biweekly journal clubs in Spanish, including previous technical tutorials to explain the tools and analyses to less experienced participants

Also, gather funding to sponsor our activities and travel fellowships for members of our community.

Additionally, we calculate and release metrics to keep track of our impact. To date, our initiatives have benefited more than 35,000 people.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: David Requena

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Yes, we collaborate with many organizations worldwide, such as the ISCB, SolBio, CABANA, and all the Latin American bioinformatics societies.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Cities across the country with technological challenges	Recorded materials available online in our website and Youtube & Facebook channels
For some topics, lack of trainers in some cities or in the country	Online courses, connecting with remote trainers
Trainers not feeling motivated to contribute	We devised a strategy of benefits for trainers including professional memberships, reciprocal training or remuneration

What is your community?

Red Mexicana de Bioinformática

Red Mexicana de Bioinformática
Mexican Bioinformatics Network

<https://www.redmexicanadebioinformatica.org/>

#BioinformaticsEducation #CDSB
#BioNetMX #RMB

How does it work?

- Hands-On Workshops (In person or virtual)
- Co-develop software tools and documentation
- Co-organize national and international events
- Disseminate scientific content to the society
- Mentoring students and researchers

Card Authors:

Dulce Valdivia and

Yalbi I. Balderas-Martínez
(Presenter)

Which is your region? And scale?

Global Map of RMB Members

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales?

We collaborate with other mexican groups, and international societies.

Lessons learned

Challenges	Solutions or strategies
Maintain an active community	Involve new people to manage the network so we can have new ideas. Collaborate with other communities to learn
Increase members	Create a web page / have social networks / a membership to access mini-courses monthly
Community distributed in a large area	Online events increase visibility

What is your community?

SIB Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics is a swiss wide institute and community that supports collaboration and knowledge sharing. An important part of this is training.

#bioinformatics #training #switzerland
#collaboration

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

- Deliver hands-on training courses
- Recruit trainers from the network
- Participate in international collaborations

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Geert van Geest

Which is your region? And scale?

Circle the one(s):

- Institution
- Group of institutes
- Area
- Country
- Continent
- Global
- Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Yes, for example within ELIXIR, EOSC and other international collaborations

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Deliver training in an ever-changing world	Recruit experts from our network to help with training
Use standards to share and reuse training materials	Participate in international collaborations and create alliances to develop standards and learn how to implement them.

What is your community?

Sociedad Iberoamericana de Bioinformática: an international scientific & professional society to promote Bioinformatics in IberoAmerica (includes 22 countries)

#bioinformatics #latinoamerica #education #computational-biology

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

Organize and Co-organize International events in our region (i.e. Latin America and IberoAmerica)

Deliver hands-on training courses. Organize Practical Workshops in Bioinformatics (In person &/or virtual)

Apply for and Coordinate International Collaborative Scientific and Research Projects.

Mentoring students and researchers in the area of Bioinformatics & Computational Biology

Disseminate scientific content to society.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Javier De Las Rivas

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text:

Circle the one(s):

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Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Please comment, and if so fill the next slide too. Otherwise, remove it.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Community distributed in a large area	Online events increase accessibility
Research topics quite specific not covered by media	Citizen science initiative to reach broader audiences
Trainers not professionally recognised	International recognition of the activities by international societies (ISCB, ECCB, SoiBio...)

What is your community?

Unidad de Ciencia de Datos en Salud
Instituto Nacional Enfermedades
Respiratorias

<https://github.com/UCDS-INER>

#DataDrivenHealth #4therighttobreath
#DataScience #HealthDigitalTransformation

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

We generate reliable data for responsible decision-making.

We encourage internal and external collaboration.

We design strategies for digital tools.

We promote open teaching and learning.

We adapt infrastructure to the capacities of the centers.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: David Escudero; Presenters: Gabriel Gomez Méndez and Yalbi I. Balderas Martínez

Which is your region? And scale?

INER is the National Institute of Respiratory Diseases in Mexico, and its data science unit likely focuses on applying advanced analytics to respiratory health data for research and clinical applications

Circle the one(s):

Institution

Group of institutes

Area

Country

Continent

Global

Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? We work in collaboration with governmental institutions, communities, and internal areas of research and teaching.

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Digital literacy and the digital divide	Implementation of digital tools to facilitate functions.
Lack of budget	Use of open-source tools
Lack of participation from interested areas	Include more areas to highlight the advantages of digitalization.

What is your community?

wellcome connecting science

Wellcome Connecting Science

Our learning and training offer spans from discovery research based on genomic technologies, to the application of genomics in healthcare and public health.

#globaltraining #genomics #bioinformatics #onlinecourses

How does it work?

List things you do in your community, to showcase how you operate. Below some examples.

Focusing on the context where your community operates, what are the lesson learned from your activity?

Card author: Alice Matimba, Monica Abrudan, Dusanka Nikolic

Which is your region? And scale?

Highlight regions in this map, or zoom in your region of interest, or represent it with any other visual or text.

Circle the one(s):

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Other:

Do you collaborate with others across regions or scales? Yes! We work with Africa, Lat AM, Asia

Lessons learned

Challenge	Solution / strategies
Data and analysis infrastructure disparities hinder learners' ability to practice bioinformatics skills.	Provide cloud-based or containerised training environments, portable toolkits, and low-cost/free open-source software to reduce technical barriers.
Trainers are unevenly distributed, with a shortage of experienced instructors in some regions	Implement "train-the-trainer" models and mentorship schemes to expand local instructor capacity and create self-sustaining training ecosystems.
Training needs vary widely depending on scale (introductory vs. advanced; local vs. international)	Develop tiered, modular standardised curricula that can be adapted to local, regional, and global levels